

Tribute Editorial

Gabriella Nucera, MD: A Remarkable Woman. A Life Devoted to Care, Faith, and Love

Francesco CHIRICO^{1*}

¹Faculty of Medicine and Surgery, Post-graduate School of Occupational Health, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Rome, Italy. E-mail: medlavchirico@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-8737-4368

Keywords: Gabriella Nucera; Editorial; Faith; Science; Tribute

Cite this paper as: Chirico F. Gabriella Nucera, MD: A Remarkable Woman. A Life Devoted to Care, Faith, and Love. Adv Med Psychol Public Health. 2026;3(1):1-3. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16494977

Received: 10 June 2025; Revised: 20 July 2025; Accepted: 27 July 2025; Published Online: 27 July 2025

One of the last questions I asked my wife Gabriella—just a few weeks before the colon cancer that had struck her so harshly began to take over—was:

"What should we do with the association we founded together?" [1].

She looked at me with that gentle firmness that had always defined her and simply replied:

"Well... can it be something useful for others?"

In that brief and disarming question lay the entire essence of her life: a life given to others, lived with love, compassion, and selflessness [2,3].

Over 24 years of shared life, I had the privilege of walking beside a woman who embodied Christian love with extraordinary consistency. Her love—for me, our children, her family, and her patients—never wavered. Gabriella was always present—even outside working hours, even during holidays—ready to respond to any request for help without hesitation [4].

Not even when, with two small children at home, she was asked to open one of the first COVID-19 units in Milan, at the Fatebenefratelli Hospital, where she was head of the emergency medicine department. At that time, she also served as acting head of the entire emergency department. She accepted without hesitation, driven by that deep sense of duty that was an integral part of her vocation [4].

It was likely during that period that the process began which, a little over a year after her cancer diagnosis, would lead to the end of her earthly life in February 2025. Twenty-one hospitalizations, one surgery, and numerous rounds of chemotherapy—faced with a dignity and strength that cannot be taught, only witnessed.

Gabriella contracted COVID-19 multiple times and developed long COVID syndrome. Despite being a fragile patient, having lived with Familial Mediterranean Fever since adolescence, she never stopped working. She continued to serve, fully aware of the risks to herself. Because to her, medicine was not just a profession—it was a calling [2-4].

She suffered from multiple drug allergies, yet in order to continue practicing, she underwent several rounds of COVID-19 vaccination, which triggered anaphylactic shocks. She also endured chronic post-COVID pericarditis and other complications, exacerbated by further allergic reactions. The stress, her weakened immune system, and professional challenges likely contributed to the development of her final illness.

Still, she never complained. Not at home, not in the hospital, not to colleagues or nurses. Only faith, courage, and silent offering. Her strength was rooted in prayer, in her unshakable trust in Jesus. She would say that pain, when lived with love, could bear fruit. And that's exactly how she lived each day of her illness: as an offering. Not showy, not loud. But deep and authentic.

Even in her final days, when the illness had spread throughout her body and not even morphine—to which she was allergic—could ease her pain (she had come close to death several times in previous years due to her multiple severe allergies), Gabriella still managed to apologize to those who were caring for her. It was in these small gestures that her true greatness revealed itself.

Gabriella left an immense void. Among patients, colleagues, and all who knew her. But she also left something even greater: a moral and spiritual legacy built on service, humility, and unwavering faith.

She taught me that life is measured by our ability to give of ourselves—not through words, but through actions. She was a quiet, humble, pragmatic woman, whose smile never faded.

Though she possessed rare spiritual gifts and a luminous inner beauty—born of her closeness to the Lord—she never sought attention. She taught me that even pain is not useless, if embraced with love. That even illness can be fruitful, if lived in the light of the Gospel.

Today, Gabriella lives on in everything she left us. In our children, Luca and Francesca, whom we hold in our hearts with infinite pride and love. She lives on in those who loved her. In those who had the fortune to know her, even briefly.

In her name, funds have already been raised for scholarships for deserving students at the Salesian Don Bosco Institute in Milan, and for a school in Congo run by the Sisters of Mary Immaculate in Rome. Even after her death, Gabriella continues to be a gift, through concrete acts of solidarity.

Gabriella will always remain with us—though in a different form. As Aldo Moro once wrote to his beloved Noretta, *"I will return, in another form."* I know that one day I will see her again, and the embrace I miss today will return—in a light that never fades.

For now, my answer is to go on. This editorial is proof of that. With a trembling heart, but eyes fixed on the example she left me. And with the will to keep serving, loving, and building.

References

1. Chirico F. Welcome to "Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health". *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(1):1-2. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10594693
2. Ferrari G, Sacco A. Tributo alla Dott.ssa Gabriella Nucera: scienza, fede e una vita al servizio degli altri [Tribute to Gabriella Nucera, MD: A life of science, faith, and selfless service]. *G Ital Psicol Med Lav*. 2025;5(1):1-5. Doi: 10.69088/2025/TRBT.

3. Ferrari G, Rizzo A, Tarchi L, Batra K. Tribute to Gabriella Nucera, MD: A life of science, faith, and selfless service. *J Health Soc Sci.* 2025;10(1):8-12. Doi: 10.19204/2025/HNRN1.
4. Chirico F, Nucera G. An Italian Experience of Spirituality from the Coronavirus Pandemic. *J Relig Health.* 2020 Oct;59(5):2193-2195. doi: 10.1007/s10943-020-01036-1.
5. Senato della Repubblica. <https://www.senato.it/service/PDF/PDFServer/BGT/908908.pdf>. Accessed on 15 Luly 2025.

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).